

At a very precise moment during the polymerization process, the synthactic foam, composed of phenolic resin and the various mineral fillers, is slowly injected between the two walls.

During this phase, the foam is deaerated to enable the part to be completely filled with a mass at very low vacuum rate.

Tests carried out on samples have made it possible to define the polymerization time: around three hours at ambient temperature for a thickness of about 50 mm.

After removal from the mould, the parts are placed in conforming jigs and undergo a stoving cycle calculated in collaboration with the resin suppliers (fig. 1).

Fig. 1

The panels are designed to allow metal inserts to be embedded in the synthactic foam. These will be used to fix the various related parts to the panel and also to support it if necessary.

Finally, the panel can be protected with a paint compatible with the materials used.

2. TESTS

Internal pre-qualification tests relating to fire-proof doors have been carried out at HAMON, in cooperation with EDF:

- 1) Compatibility tests on the products used.
- 2) Fire resistance tests.
- 3) Sagging tests
- 4) Delamination tests.
- 5) Impact resistance tests.
- 6) Water recovery tests.

Some of these tests have been confirmed by accredited laboratories, viz:

- Fire resistance tests at the Centre Technique Industriel de la Construction Métallique (CTICM) at Maizières les Metz.
- Mechanical resistance tests at EDF's Centre d'Essais de Matériaux et d'Etudes des Techniques d'Exécution (CEMETE) at Aix en Provence.
- M and F classification tests at the Centre Scientifique et Technique du Bâtiment (CSTB) at Marne la Vallée.

2.1. Fire resistance test of a double-leaf door of 2290 x 1848 mm.

2.1.1. Method

Three of the doors to be tested are delivered to an accredited laboratory (CTICM) to be tested front and back in an oven of the appropriate dimensions. The third door acts as a reference.

Before firing, very precise measurements of the leaves are taken, the doors are opened and closed 2000 times and undergo an airtightness test.

Fire resistance testing is performed as per standard ISO 834 . The leaves are fitted with a number of thermocouples and displacements sensors necessary for obtaining approval.

During the test, the temperature within the oven must be adjusted in accordance with the following equation:

$$T - T_0 = 345 \log_{10} (8t + 1) \text{ (see curve fig. 2).}$$

t = time expressed in min.

T = oven temperature in °C at time t

T₀ = initial oven temperature in °C.

The test is stopped when the functions of heat insulation and (or) airtightness are no longer operative.

The airtightness factor is measured using a dry cotton swab which, when passed around the edge of the door, must not burst into flame.

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

2.1.2. Test results

2.1.2.1. Definitions

Flame-resistant element: an element with a wall which, when not exposed to fire, can exceed 140°C while remaining flameproof.

Fire-resistant element: an element with a wall which, when not exposed to fire, does not exceed 140°C while remaining flameproof.

The levels at temperature do not take into account the ambient temperature

2.1.2.1.2. Results

The doors made of the composite Sandwich panel were approved as fire and flame resistant for 1h 30 min. The smoke extractor shutters were approved for 2 hours.

It must be noted that the temperature of the wall which was not exposed to fire never exceeded 70°C as can be seen on the curve fig. 3 (see photos fig. 4, 5 and 6).

Fig. 4
Exterior of the oven
before the test

Fig 5
Exterior of the oven
after the test

Fig 6
Interior of the oven after the test

2.2. Mechanical resistance tests

2.2.1. Method

EDF's specifications require the doors to undergo without damage 400.000 opening and closing operations of different kinds, representing conditions encountered in practice.

These tests, performed by CEMETE, consist of opening the leaf to be tested by means of a hydraulic ram driven by a programmer.

The cycle is compatible if the opening angle exceeds 60° . During the test, a detailed and systematic inspection enables the behavior of the equipment being tested to be accounted for.

2.2.2. Result

The composite leaf, given its lightness and resistance, showed no damage after 450.000 cycles.

The leaf tested mechanically was then approved as fire/flame resistant for 1h 30 min.

CONCLUSIONS

The conclusive tests described above mean that the Sandwich panel is suitable for use in various fields: fire doors, smoke extraction shutters, ventilation ducts and partitions for high-risk rooms.

Studies are in progress with the main suppliers of railway stock and oil tankers.

A product such as this is suitable for use on the Transmanche high speed trains, for which problems of fire resistance and weight need to be taken into consideration, as is also the case for offshore oil rigs.

As the product does not corrode, a use could also be found for it in the internal equipment of ships such as tankers, ore carriers or warships.

Initially, EDF plans to equip its nuclear power plants with these fire doors.